

POLITICAL MEMORY AS AGONISTIC PRACTICE ON SOCIAL MEDIA: MEMORIFICATION, SEMIO-SOMATIC MEMORY, MULTIMODALITY, AND AFFORDANCES THEORIZED THROUGH THE DIGITAL CIRCULATION OF THE SLOGAN “SMRT FAŠIZMU, SVOBODA NARODU”

ABSTRACT

In recent decades, digital platforms have become central spaces for reshaping cultural memory. Slogans like “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” reappear within algorithmically curated environments, where users repeat, adapt, and challenge them in relation to current ideological struggles. The article argues that the political power of digital memory comes from reactivating *historically sedimented semio-somatic memory* – embodied mnemonic forms created through ritual repetition and collective action – within platform-based systems of visibility. We understand these transformations as processes of *memorification*: the accelerated circulation and redefinition of mnemonic forms in algorithmically organized environments. In these settings, mnemonic authority shifts from mainly top-down institutional regulation toward more bottom-up, platform-mediated dynamics of visibility and affective resonance. Digital memory operates within a new memory ecosystem, where historically embodied forms become sites of agonistic contestation over meaning, legitimacy, and power in the present.

KEYWORDS: digital memory, semio-somatic memory, memorification, agonistic public sphere, platform affordances, multimodality and embodiment, political memory.

IZVLEČEK

V zadnjih desetletjih so digitalne platforme postale osrednje arene preoblikovanja kulturnega spomina. Gesla, kot je »Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu«, se znova pojavljajo v algoritmično kuriranih okoljih, kjer jih uporabniki ponavljajo, prilagajajo in problematizirajo v povezavi s sodobnimi političnimi boji. Članek zagovarja tezo, da politična moč digitalnega spomina izhaja iz ponovne aktivacije *zgodovinsko sedimentiranega semio-somatskega spomina* – utelešenih mnemoničnih oblik, oblikovanih skozi ritualno ponavljanje in kolektivno uprizorjanje – znotraj platformnih infrastruktur vidnosti. Ta premik razumeva kot proces *memorifikacije*, ki označuje pospešeno kroženje in ponovno artikulacijo mnemoničnih oblik v algoritmično strukturiranih okoljih. V teh pogojih se mnemonična avtoriteta premika od pretežno institucionalne regulacije pomena od zgoraj navzdol k bolj od spodaj navzgor usmerjenim, platformno posredovanim dinamikam vidnosti in afektivne resonance. Digitalni spomin deluje znotraj nove ekologije spomina, v kateri zgodovinsko utelešene oblike postajajo mesta agonističnega spopadanja glede pomena, legitimnosti in razmerij moči v sedanosti.

KLJUČNE BESEDE: digitalni spomin, semio-somatski spomin, memorifikacija, agonistična javnost, platformne zmožnosti delovanja, multimodalnost in utelešene prakse, politični spomin.

SUMMARY

Digital platforms have become key spaces for revitalizing and challenging cultural memory. The article claims that the political power of digital memory comes from reactivating historically embodied and ritualized mnemonic forms within platformed infrastructures of visibility. Drawing on memory studies, multimodality, and affordance theory, the article conceptualizes these processes through the notion of *semio-somatic memory* highlighting how mnemonic expressions endure and gain political impact through the sedimentation of bodily practices, sensory modalities, and semiotic structures. Under contemporary conditions, mnemonic authority shifts from mainly top-down institutional control of meaning to more bottom-up, platform-driven processes of visibility, circulation, and affective resonance, partially democratizing the creation and contestation of public memory.

The argument is developed through a multimodal examination of how the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” circulates on X and Facebook today. Originating from the WWII Yugoslav partisan resistance, the slogan originally served as a confrontational and mobilizing performative act. In post-war socialist Yugoslavia, it was institutionalized and ritualized, becoming part of state ceremonies and educational activities, where its antagonistic power was partially diminished even as it became deeply embodied and internalized. During these initial stages, the slogan accumulated a layered semio-somatic charge through repetition, collective vocalization, and bodily enactment. In the post-socialist and digital era, this embodied mnemonic significance allows for its reactivation and resignification within new political contexts. The case shows how embodied mnemonic forms endure across different political regimes and media landscapes, being reactivated, resignified, and contested in present-day political struggles. Rather than functioning as stable references to the past, these forms serve as active political interventions within agonistic public spheres.

This transformation can be understood as *memorification*: the accelerated activation and recirculation of historically sedimented mnemonic forms within algorithmically structured environments. Digital memory, therefore, becomes a form of political contestation where embodiment, multimodality, and platform affordances jointly condition public visibility and mobilization.

INTRODUCTION

In academic circles, it is nearly undeniable that digital platforms have become central environments in which memory is now experienced and shaped (Hoskins, 2011a; Hoskins, 2018; van Dijck, 2013; van Dijck et al., 2018). The collective act of remembering, once largely organized through traditional institutions such as museums, archives, education, and mass media, is now increasingly mediated by digital social platforms and their multimodal, interactive structures. These environments introduce new layers of technical and semiotic mediation, where digital design and algorithmic logic influence how the past is reshaped into publicly perceptible and affectively charged forms (Birkner and Donk, 2018; Hoskins, 2024a; Bucher, 2018).

Remembering (and forgetting) has thus become both informal in practice and institutionalized within platform infrastructure, marking what Andrew Hoskins has described as a connective turn in contemporary memory cultures (Hoskins, 2011b). Mnemonic expressions increasingly emerge through everyday digital practices in which users collectively produce and remix memory across multiple expressive forms, yet their circulation and visibility remain structured by algorithmic systems and platform governance. Personal recollections reappear through algorithmic prompts and “memories” features, while collective histories are reassembled through platform-native mechanisms such as tagging and recommender systems and algorithmic curation. What earlier regimes stabilized through institutional selection, archiving (with expert object annotation, established metadata taxonomies, and classificatory relations), and presentation within relatively enclosed reception contexts – such as exhibitions, official commemorations, and legacy media (Bennett, 1995; Assmann, 2011) – is now reactivated through algorithmic circulation and user co-authorship. Instead of stabilizing mnemonic authority through institutional curation, digital infrastructures condition how mnemonic forms resurface and gain prominence within feedback-driven interactional environments (Hoskins, 2024b). Within this new memory ecology (cf. Brown and Hoskins, 2010), institutional authority remains; it operates within reorganized conditions where remembering and forgetting are shaped by platform architectures as much as by formal selection. These dynamics intensify with legacy institutional efforts toward platformization, networkization, and user co-authoring engagement (Ringel and Ribak, 2024), the rise of AI-driven curation, and dedicated memory applications. Institutional authority persists but now functions within a hybrid ecology in which institutional materials circulate alongside vernacular and user-generated content.

The article argues that the political power of digital memory arises where historically sedimented embodied forms meet platform-specific conditions of action. Digital social media transform cultural memory from a mainly top-down, institutionally controlled system into grassroots, platform-mediated practices of public remembrance, thereby redistributing mnemonic authority and partially democratizing the creation and contestation of public memory. While multimodality explains why certain mnemonic forms remain affectively potent and recognizable over time, platform affordances explain how – and under what conditions – this affective force becomes activated in public arenas and drawn into political confrontation. Memory is thus viewed as a political practice that functions in the present and influences current power relations. These processes of redistribution, multimodal activation, and platform-conditioned visibility are explored through digital circulation of the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu,” which demonstrates how semiotic and embodied – semio-somatic – memory forms are reactivated and contested on social media. The article approaches digital

memory from a praxeological perspective, considering it an embodied and semiotic *practice* whose political impact depends on the interaction of historically sedimented mnemonic forms, platform affordances and the potential for multimodal articulation of meaning. By examining how the slogan is activated and contested on X and Facebook, the analysis situates platformed remembrance within broader discussions of agonistic public memory and democratic debate.

MEMORY IN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENTS

While digital platforms redistribute mnemonic production toward vernacular and user-generated practices, they also establish a new form of institutional governance rooted in commercial interests. Platform infrastructure is mainly managed by profit-focused companies whose primary aims are to increase engagement metrics, capture attention, and provoke emotional reactions. The visibility and circulation of memory are increasingly shaped not by historical significance or contributions to public discussion but by these platform-specific metrics.

The digital transformation of the public sphere has resulted in what is known as its *communification* – the widespread integration of communication technologies into everyday life and the subjugation of communicative processes to institutional privatization (Splichal, 2024). In these conditions, communication is no longer a separate domain of public exchange but a foundational infrastructure embedded within commercial platform architectures. If memory is understood – as Wolfgang Ernst (2017), Daniel Salerno (2021), and others suggest – as innate to communicative processes both techno-socially and semiotically, then the communification of the public sphere entails a parallel transformation: communication itself increasingly functions as a mnemonic process. The ongoing recalibration of communicative life into processes of activation, circulation, and sedimentation across commercial social media platforms constitutes *memorification*.

Existing research on digital and political memory primarily focuses on representational, discursive, informational, and technological aspects of remembering – highlighting communication but often neglecting the embodied and sensorimotor dimensions through which memory acquires affective force. This limitation is evident not only in memory studies but also in media and platform research and in political theories. It is less prominent in multimodal scholarship, where embodiment is usually secondary to questions of mode, medium, or signification.

Memory, Power, and Political Actuality

Memory does not derive its legitimacy from accuracy to the past but from its relevance in the present. Unlike historiography, which has traditionally aimed to distance itself from memory to establish factual accuracy, memory studies emphasize that references to the past gain meaning through their current significance, meaning their ability to address ongoing matters that range from intimate experience to collective and political issues. As Jan Assmann has argued, the “truth” of memory lies not so much in its factual accuracy as in its relevance (Assmann, 1997, 9–10).

Memory is selective and interest-driven, making it inherently open to intervention. As Edward Said notes, “the processes of memory are frequently, if not always, manipulated and intervened for sometimes urgent purposes in the present” (Said, 2000, 179). Institutions and

social groups do not simply inherit memories; they actively create them through symbols, narratives, and commemorative practices (Assmann, 2008, 55) that reinforce certain interpretations of the past while marginalizing others. Since memory functions through selective activation and suppression, it influences current power dynamics connected to identity claims and struggles for legitimacy. This political aspect becomes especially prominent in digital spaces, where processes of remembering and forgetting are intensified and publicly contested.

Memory is structured through relations of power that determine which pasts are publicly activated and which are kept silent. As Aleida Assmann has demonstrated, cultural memory operates through a distinction between the canon and the archive: the canon comprises narratives that are actively shared and normatively reinforced, while the archive holds preserved materials that remain politically dormant (Assmann, 2010). Systems of memory are therefore also systems of forgetting, in which exclusion and omission act as organized mechanisms rather than as random loss. What is publicly remembered is inherently linked to what is systematically made invisible.

Michel Foucault's concept of *counter-memory* offers terminology for analyzing these struggles. Counter-memory refers to practices that challenge dominant historical narratives by reactivating marginalized pasts and exposing the power relations embedded in regimes of remembrance (Foucault, 1977). As Davis and Starn (1989) point out, counter-memory does not just recover suppressed content but functions through strategic remembering that resists enforced silence and questions established frameworks of historical authority. In this way, counter-memory shows that memory conflicts are not rare moments of disruption, but recurrent interventions through which claims to legitimacy and historical meaning are continuously contested.

This political and present-focused view of memory is further developed in approaches that see memory as mobile and ongoing, such as Astrid Erll's concept of "travelling memory" (2011) and Amanda Barnier and Andrew Hoskins' description of "memory in the wild" (2018). Memory is not tied to a single medium, institution, or authoritative narrative, but circulates through continuous processes of mediation, translation, and recontextualization across social and historical settings. As memories travel, they do not retain a stable or original meaning but are constantly rephrased in relation to new actors, interests, and power relations (Erll, 2011). This view is especially relevant for understanding digital memory cultures, where mnemonic forms quickly circulate across platforms, formats, and audiences. The mobility of memory increases its political importance: as references to the past shift between contexts, they become sites of continuous reinterpretation and contested public debates. disagreement. However, mobility does not displace the importance of the sedimentation of mnemonic forms; rather, historically layered meanings periodically crystallize in specific communicative conjunctures. They gain political strength when they are revived in new communicative settings – places where remembering becomes both a mode of discourse and a mode of political intervention. Sedimentation provides the structured forms through which memory becomes intelligible, and politically operative.

This tension becomes especially noticeable in digital memory cultures, where mnemonic forms quickly spread across platforms, formats, and audiences. Under faster mediation, processes of de-sedimentation and re-sedimentation happen more quickly, giving the impression of constant instability as references to the past are repeatedly mobilized, contested, and displaced. Memory thus functions less as a store of fixed meanings and more

as a dynamic process in which historically sedimented forms are continuously modulated through circulation, mediation, and struggle in the present. As the following analysis demonstrates, the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” illustrates this dynamic, maintaining political efficacy not as a stable discursive reference but as a historically ritualized and embodied mnemonic form that remains accessible for reactivation under contemporary conditions.

The slogan today circulates across different mnemonic registers. It may appear as a nostalgic invocation of the socialist anti-fascist canon, and it can also act as a site of counter-memory, reopening silenced or marginalized aspects of that regime. At the same time, it undergoes further semantic transformations that go beyond both nostalgia and critique. These changes, however, do not detach it from the past; they draw their strength precisely from historically sedimented and embodied memory, which allows the slogan to stay recognizable while embracing new political expressions.

The Digital Shift: From the Regulation of Meaning to the Regulation of Visibility

Earlier regimes of cultural memory derived authority from their capacity to stabilize legitimate interpretations of the past. Digital platforms, by contrast, reorganize mnemonic power around conditions of visibility and circulation rather than interpretive closure. Authority no longer rests primarily on defining what the past means, but on shaping which references to the past become perceptible, repeatable, and affectively resonant in public space.

This shift has important political consequences. Struggles over memory are increasingly fought over algorithmically intensified exposure instead of being settled within institutions. Mnemonic power arises through iterative interaction and affective involvement, embedding memory in ongoing public contests. Digital platforms change the conditions that keep memory active in public. While institutional actors still influence memory cultures, they now operate within a hybrid environment where platform circulation intersects with grassroots practices. The following sections expand on this framework by examining how platform features and multimodal expression shape the use of memory in political conflict in digital spaces.

The reconfiguration of mnemonic power from authoritative meaning-making to platform-mediated visibility has significant implications for the public sphere. When remembering is structured by algorithmic exposure and emotional uptake, memory practices move into the realm of political contestation rather than agreement. Instead of reinforcing shared narratives of the past, platform-mediated remembering often leads to competing claims about what should be remembered, how, and by whom.

Chantal Mouffe’s concept of the agonistic public sphere (2013) offers a helpful framework for understanding these dynamics, highlighting conflict as a core element of democratic life. When applied to memory cultures, this indicates that struggles over remembrance and forgetting are not anomalies from a stable historical consensus but are expressions of ongoing disputes over identity, legitimacy, and power. Digital platforms amplify these agonistic dynamics by enabling multiple, often conflicting memory claims to be visible, circulate broadly, and mobilize affective responses within the same public space.

EMBODIMENT, MULTIMODALITY, AND SEMIO-SOMATIC MEMORY

The analysis now shifts to historically embodied and ritualized forms of remembering that existed before digital media but still influence their online revival. The focus is not on platform infrastructures themselves but on the semio-somatic dispositions ingrained through earlier ritual practices and reinterpreted within platformed environments. Instead of being replaced by digital mediation, these embodied memories – opposing purely modal or mental representations (Iani, 2019) – persist and are reshaped through platform-specific multimodal discourse. The article argues that embodiment must be recognized as an important aspect of digital memory, which is often overlooked in memory and multimodal research, where emphasis generally goes to representational modes and sensory channels at the expense of embodied and ritualized enactment and the somatic nature of memory itself (cf. Campbell et al., 2019; Iani, 2019).

In digital platform environments, the political efficacy of mnemonic forms depends on how embodied dispositions are reactivated through multimodal configurations. Affordances and multimodal expressions influence whether historically sedimented memory remains inactive or becomes active in the present. The reactivation of historically sedimented mnemonic forms relies on culturally recognizable discursive configurations and shared semantic vocabularies (cf. Greimas, 1987; Eco et al., 1989). In platform settings, these patterns are rearticulated through the activation of historically embodied and ritualized forms, whose affective force is modulated by specific affordances and multimodal expression.

Two key points are here: the inseparability of perceptual, sensory, and semiotic dimensions, and the impossibility of strictly separating "dis-embodied" and "embodied" memories (Lagerkvist, 2016). Many ideas about affordances in digital media research assume embodiment but rarely explicitly highlight it. Embodiment, seen as our relationship to the world, forms a foundational "ur-relation" that underpins the link between material substrates and action possibilities (Gibson, 2015). This aligns with cognitive scientific accounts of memory as an adaptive ability that supports agency in response to environmental demands, particularly with the symbol-grounding hypothesis, which states that symbols gain meaning through sensorimotor experience (Iani 2019, 1747–1748).

Concepts such as "media ecology" and "memory ecology" already situate memory within environmental relations (Lagerkvist, 2016), the emphasis of the article's argument is in defining the environment as both semiotic and somatic. We examine semio-somatic memory from a diachronic perspective and do not explore the formation of new somatic memories specific to digital platforms. Social-media-specific sensorimotor practices (such as clicking, scrolling, and finger gesturing), while important in their own right, are not subject of article's focus. . Instead, the focus is on the persistence of earlier embodied practices and their re-embodiment on social media platforms, as well as their relevance for political memory. The political effectiveness of memory in the present stems from the activation of historically ritualized mnemonic forms through multimodal configurations that enable their rearticulation and contestation across different contexts.

Multimodality as a Political Force of Memory

Multimodality is essential for understanding the political force of memory because memory is constituted through embodied, sensory, and semiotic processes that arguably precede and

exceed any specific technological setting. To explore questions about platform affordances and digital circulation, it is important to clarify how meaning and affect converge to create political intensity through the interaction among bodily practices, perceptual processes, and semiotic material forms.

In multimodal theory, a key distinction is made between semiotic modes and sensory modalities. Based on social-semiotic approaches developed by Gunther Kress and Theo van Leeuwen (Kress and Van Leeuwen, 2006), modes are seen as socially and culturally shaped semiotic resources – such as language, images, sounds, gestures, and layouts among others – each with its own potential for meaning and conventions. Modes are not neutral transmitters of information; rather, they are structured systems of meaning-making that are historically sedimented and socially regulated; they are habitualized practices. The concept of modality, as used here, following multimodal theorists, refers to sensory modalities (Kress, 2010; Bateman and Wildfeuer, 2014; Forceville, 2006): the sensory channels through which modes are apprehended – visual, auditory, and tactile/kinesthetic, modalities (among others). Sensory modalities influence how semiotic modes are perceived, integrated, and affectively experienced.

Multimodal research distinguishes three analytically separate yet interconnected dimensions: (1) sensorial channels (e.g., vision, hearing, bodily movement), (2) perceptual integration through which sensory input is combined and organized, and (3) semiotic modes, which convey culturally mediated meanings (cf. Kress, 2010; Bateman et al., 2017; and Oja, 2023).

A common issue in communication and memory studies is that these dimensions are often conflated. Multimodality is frequently used as a catch-all term, while in practice it refers primarily to the coexistence of text, images, and sounds, or to the multimedia character of digital artifacts. Consequently, analyses tend to remain descriptive, emphasizing media formats rather than exploring the relationships among semiotic modes, sensory modalities, and socio-technical affordances. This conceptual slippage is particularly consequential for memory studies. When multimodality is reduced to a combination of media forms, the embodied and ritual dimensions through which memory acquires affective and political force are obscured.

Memory, as enacted through bodily practices – gestures, vocalizations, rhythms, and repetitions – can be seen as a kind of “semiotic scaffolding acquired by learning” as it that bind sensory experience to shared symbolic frameworks (Campbell et al., 2019, 356). Although multimodal theories foreground the material base of meaning-making, they often miss the role of embodiment when semiotic resources are treated primarily as culturally available forms rather than as enacted in and through the environment. As Campbell et al. (2019, 358) argue, referencing James J. Gibson’s (2015) idea of affordances, “semiotic resources [as affordances] are not just anything in the environment, but anything that an organism’s sense perceptive and motoric capabilities evoke as available.”

The political importance of memory cannot be understood without considering both its semiotic materiality and its somatic (sensory-perceptual and sensorimotor) aspect. As Kress (2010, 157) highlights, the affordances of modes “rest on the materiality of the stuff” from which signs are made, even though this materiality is socially shaped into cultural semiotic resources. Therefore, meaning is not purely discursive, cognitive, or somatic; it develops through historically situated practices that connect material form, sensory perception, and social convention.

Multimodal theorists emphasize that meaning is co-constructed across modes, rather than found in any single mode alone (Kress and Van Leeuwen, 2006; Bateman et al., 2017). The political and mnemonic power of an expression depends as much on bodily enactment, sensory perception, and collective repetition as on semantic content and modal composition. The more inter-semiotically complex the multimodal configuration is, the more expansive is its intermodal meaning potential, as well as its potential for affective charge.

The political intensity of certain mnemonic expressions arises from their prior ritualization and embodied repetition. Through sustained collective actions, ideological meanings become sedimented as bodily dispositions – internalized through voice, posture, rhythm, and synchronized performance. This early habituation forms the mnemonic substrate from which current reactivations draw their force. In post-socialist digital environments, such expressions no longer function within the institutional rituals that once grounded them, but their political efficacy persists precisely because they still activate historically internalized forms. Multimodality is crucial here: it facilitates the reexpression of sedimented embodied memory across textual, visual, and gestural configurations, allowing both affirmative and critical political expressions to surface today. Positioning multimodality at this fundamental level highlights an approach to memory as practice – a process in which ideological meanings are sedimented, internalized, and made experientially compelling.

MNEMONIC ENDURANCE OF THE SLOGAN “SMRT FAŠIZMU, SVOBODA NARODU”

The analysis in this section traces how the slogan is activated and rendered contestable in platformed environments, thereby shifting attention from memory as representation to memory as practice within contemporary political struggles.

The slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu,” originates in the WWII Yugoslav resistance against the occupying Axis Powers. Although the exact point of origin is difficult to discern from available documentation – it is clear that it became particularly widespread during the summer of 1941 when it began to circulate (on posters and official correspondence) within the partisan movement.¹ (fig. 1)

¹ The Kingdom of Yugoslavia joined the Tripartite Pact, the Axis alliance between Germany, Italy, and Japan, on 25 March 1941 under strong geopolitical pressure. Two days later, however, a military coup in Belgrade overthrew the government that had signed the pact. In April 1941 the country was invaded by Axis forces, rapidly defeated, and partitioned among occupying powers, giving rise to both collaboration and resistance. In the first months of occupation, resistance activities largely took political, organizational, and cultural forms, including the establishment of clandestine networks, the circulation of illegal publications, and other forms of opposition to the occupying regimes, involving a variety of political actors. Notably, in the territory of Slovenian Littoral, the anti-fascist militant group TIGR began its armed activities against the occupiers as early as in May 1941. At that time Nazi Germany and the Soviet Union were still bound by the Molotov–Ribbentrop non-aggression pact of 1939, during which the Comintern interpreted the war as an imperialist conflict between capitalist states. After the German attack on the Soviet Union on 22 June 1941 (Operation Barbarossa), the Communist Party of Yugoslavia initiated and expanded the organization of its armed resistance. During this period the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” began to circulate widely.

Fig. 1: Early partisan poster dated July 7, 1941, featuring the slogan “Death to Fascism, Freedom to the People” (Serbian Cyrillic: „Смрт фашизму, слобода народу“), along with an image of a clenched fist as a symbol of resistance.

Semiotically, the slogan condenses existing European antifascist signifiers – most notably the formula “death to fascism,” which circulated during the Spanish Civil War – into a binary structure that pairs negation with an emancipatory promise. It quickly spread across various forms of communication: printed leaflets and bulletins, partisan press, graffiti, correspondence, and everyday speech. It served both as a greeting and a farewell, replacing the traditional language and gestural conventions and norms of everyday address – embedding political opposition into daily interactions. Its abbreviation (“SF–SN”), numerous public inscriptions, and reported heroic vocalization during moments of intense combat confrontation indicate that it acted as a performative act of collective identity. In this context, its discursive economy and affective intensity invite comparison with “¡No pasarán!” of the Spanish Civil War.

After World War II, the slogan became increasingly associated with an image of the resistance fighter Stjepan Filipović, who was photographed just before his execution and is said to have spoken the slogan in the final moments, with raised and clenched fists (fig. 2).² Especially after its public release in *Politika* on November 4, 1944, the photograph of Filipović became a symbol of partisan resistance; after the war it circulated publicly, and gained an iconic status. His signature defiant pose was replicated in statues (notably in Opuzen and Valjevo, figs. 3 and 4), on an official Yugoslav stamp, and later even outside of the Yugoslav context as an international symbol of resistance, including at the Holocaust Museum in New York.

² Stjepan Filipović was executed in Valjevo on May 27, 1942, at the age of twenty-six. According to SS reports, he shouted anti-fascist and pro-communist slogans while being led through the streets (Radanović 2012) urging the locals to take on arms and fight against the occupiers (Konjikušić, 2017, 139). Immediately before his execution, at least as is widely reported and circulated, he raised his arms, clenched his fists, and cried out “Smrt fašizmu, sloboda narodu.” While this exact last words cannot be definitively verified, collective memory has condensed these reports into the recognisable phrasing of the slogan, which captures both the event and his defiant stance at the gallows. Slobodanka Vasić, a young apprentice at the Kosara photographic studio in Valjevo, most likely took the photograph. According to later testimonies, the image was briefly offered for sale by the studio after the execution, before a German raid confiscated and destroyed the negative and most prints; some reproductions nevertheless entered clandestine circulation (see Konjikušić, 2017).

Fig. 2: Slobodanka Vasić, Stjepan Filipović beneath the gallows in Valjevo, Serbia, on May 22, 1942, just before his execution. With his fists raised and clenched, he became a lasting symbol of partisan resistance, widely remembered for the slogan “Death to fascism, freedom to the people.”

Figures 3 and 4: Postwar monumentalization: cultural memorization and mythologization of the WWII resistance movement. Figure 3 (left) shows the monument to Stjepan Filipović in Valjevo, Serbia (sculptor Vojin Bakić, erected 1960), which still stands today. Figure 4 (right) shows the monument in Opuzen, Croatia (sculptors Miro Vuco and Stjepan Gračan, erected in 1978), which was demolished in 1991 during the Yugoslav breakup wars by Croatian nationalists.

In this process of public circulation and institutional reproduction, the image stopped serving only as a record of a single execution and instead became a condensed visual symbol of occupation violence, resistance memory, and post-war socialist narrative formation. Crucially, the difficulty of retrospectively distinguishing the slogan’s genesis, its association with Filipović’s posture, and its subsequent performances in schools and public ceremonies is not an obstacle but an indicator of its ritualized character. Ritual tends to erase contextual

specificity, operating through repetition and bodily habit rather than conscious reflection. What endures is less the memory of specific events than a corporeal disposition: a learned way of standing, speaking, responding, and aligning oneself with a shared symbolic order. In this way, ritualized mnemonic practices act as tools for internalization, embedding ideological orientations in bodily habits rather than explicit beliefs.

During WWII and afterward, within socialist Yugoslavia, the slogan functioned as a collective performative articulated through ritualized actment: standing posture, forceful vocalization, coordinated bodily gestures (such as body orientation and a raised fist), and synchronized collective utterances in partisan meetings and other settings. These practices engaged multiple sensory modalities simultaneously – auditory, visual, proprioceptive, and kinesthetic – tying the slogan to embodied experience and not to abstract cognition alone. Through repetition in institutional and public contexts during the war and later in the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (including Slovenia until 1991), the slogan became embedded in bodily memory, acquiring force beyond its propositional content.

Speech act theory provides useful, though limited, conceptual vocabulary for understanding this dynamic. In John Austin's terms, the slogan did not merely describe a political stance; it did something: it enacted allegiance, opposition, and collective positioning through its utterance (Austin, 1962). Judith Butler's reworking of performativity further emphasizes that such force does not come from a single act but from iterability – from repeated enactments that stabilize meaning through citation and ritual repetition (Butler, 1997). In the case of "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu," performativity was not solely a property of language but of a multimodal ensemble in which speech was inseparable from bodily disposition and collective rhythm.

A brief comparison with the slogan "Za domovino, s Titom naprej" ("For our homeland, we move forward with Tito")³ helps clarify how mnemonic endurance functions in "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu." The former was highly ritualized and routinely performed in post-WWII Yugoslav daily institutional settings, especially in schools. It also depended on repetition, collective vocalization, and bodily synchronization to foster ideological alignment. In primary schools, classes usually started with a standard call-and-response performance: the teacher – or a designated pupil – would stand before the class and utter the initial phrase "Za domovino," to which the pupils responded together, "S Titom naprej." The slogan was also linked to the Pionir pledge – a formal oath children took when joining the Pioniri, the youth organization of socialist Yugoslavia. Recited collectively during a ceremony – usually at age seven – it outlined a normative framework through which children were integrated into the moral, political, and symbolic order of the socialist state. While the pledge expressed a broad ethical and political program – encompassing diligence, comradeship, loyalty to the partisan legacy, internationalist solidarity, and affective attachment to the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia – the badge given upon becoming a Pionir displayed the slogan "Za domovino, s Titom naprej," condensing these commitments into a compact visual and textual symbol.

Yet despite these similarities with "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu," the slogan with Tito did not become a lasting political mnemonic form in later periods and mostly faded from use in independent Slovenia. This difference suggests that ritualization and embodiment alone do not ensure mnemonic longevity. They create conditions for mnemonic force that can later be

³ Josip Broz Tito (1892–1980) was a Yugoslav revolutionary who led the Partisan resistance during the Second World War and became the leader of socialist Yugoslavia from 1945 until his death.

reactivated or not, depending on semiotic structure and broader historical and political factors.

What sets apart slogans that endure from those that fade is less their level of ritualization than their ability for resignification. In the case of “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu,” the embodied and affective charge generated through ritual repetition provides conditions for its rearticulation in new political contexts, especially as its original historical reference becomes partly obscured. The slogan is also characterized by a strongly oppositional semiotic structure. Its endurance is maintained through repeated enactment and through a linguistic configuration where political meaning is generated relationally rather than referentially: fascism and freedom are positions defined through negation, so that the rejection of fascism acts as the formal condition for the affirmation of freedom. By embedding political opposition directly into its linguistic form, the slogan distills a complex political stance into a durable and easily mobilizable utterance. Importantly, its semiotic “clarity” notwithstanding, the slogan remains underdetermined in a way associated with floating or partly empty signifiers, whose meaning is stabilized contingently through discursive articulation rather than by fixed referential content. The repeatability of the slogan’s formulaic configuration allows metonymic displacement, enabling successive enemies and groups to be inscribed into the same structural positions, while the rhythmic symmetry and evaluative asymmetry of the opposition sustain its affective charge. The slogan’s political efficacy is therefore anchored in the tension between syntagmatic invariance and paradigmatic variability, allowing for a continuity of the form alongside semantic rearticulation within shifting discursive formations. By contrast, “Za domovino, s Titom naprej” cannot function in the same way, since it lacks a relational opposition that generates meaning through negation and ties its significance to the explicit figure of a former Yugoslav president, anchoring interpretation to a specific historical reference rather than a structurally reproducible opposition.

From Ritualization to Resignification: Three Phases in the Use of the Slogan

The persistence of “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” cannot be explained by a single historical context or political regime. Its durability comes from a series of transformations through which the slogan has been repeatedly re-embedded in changing configurations of power, memory, and embodiment. These transformations can be broken down into three interconnected phases: (1) the emergence of the slogan during the revolutionary and resistance efforts of WWII Yugoslavia; (2) its post-war institutionalization in the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia; and (3) its reactivation during the transitional and post-socialist periods, including today’s contexts. Each phase features a different relationship between ritual, authority, and political function.

In its initial stage, the slogan arose within partisan resistance as a revolutionary and mobilizing utterance under conditions of foreign military occupation. Established in a context in which occupying forces maintained political and territorial control, the slogan served as an explicitly oppositional, anti-occupation performative statement. Although produced within a politically organized movement led by the Communist Party, it operated under conditions of existential threat and violent repression. Its performative force lay in its ability to articulate a collective stance in a situation of armed conflict and occupation, where speech, bodily presence, and risk intertwined. During this phase, the slogan was a performative act of alignment enacted through embodied multimodal practices.

Following the war, the political actor that had mobilized the slogan within resistance – the Communist Party – became the ruling authority. The slogan was not abandoned; instead, it was carried into the new political order by the very actors who had previously used it in opposition. However, its role fundamentally shifted. What once embodied performative resistance under occupation became, in the post-war era, a commemorative tool embedded in state power. The conflict that initially defined its use was no longer active and had been resolved. The slogan’s antagonistic force was displaced from the present confrontation to the memory of past conflict. Integrated into state-sponsored rituals, school practices, national commemorations, and official memory culture, it became a stable part of the socialist symbolic order (figs. 5 and 6). Through ritual repetition, it no longer motivated collective action against an existing authority but instead confirmed the legitimacy of the authority now in control.

Figure 5: Post-war public ceremony beneath the banner “Death to fascism, freedom to the people.” The slogan supported the socialist symbolic order through ritualized, collective enactment in institutional settings and commemorative celebrations.

Figure 6: Official post-war administrative document (Ljubljana, December 1, 1945) ending with the salute “Smrt fašizmu – svoboda narodu.” The slogan was used as a formal closing greeting in both spoken and written bureaucratic correspondence.

While the slogan continued to evoke freedom, this appeal was channeled through an authoritarian one-party political system. Its rebellious energy was redirected toward a narrative of antifascist victory and the prevention of perceived external and internal threats, thus anchoring state authority in the memory of communist-led resistance. In this second phase, the slogan mainly served as a legitimizing memory: it reinforced the ideological link between the Party, the Partisan struggle, and the socialist state, naturalizing their inseparability.

The third phase occurs in the post-socialist era after Slovenia's independence, when socialist memory regimes dissolved and institutional monopolies over public remembrance weakened. At the same time, previously suppressed memories resurfaced. In this context, "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu" lost its clear institutional support and re-entered public debate as a contested, politically charged sign. Its reemergence on social media – particularly X and Facebook – does not depend on detailed historical knowledge of its origins but on affective and bodily dispositions sedimented through earlier rituals and habitual practices.

The Capacity for Resignification

Because collective memories are generational and constantly evolving, it is hard to identify a single way the slogan works in today's social media environments, especially when considering the somatic aspect of memory and its relation to different semiotic modes, sensory experiences, and platform features. Still, the significance of the slogan relies on the specific ways memory forms within different cultural settings. The following explanation outlines its main multimodal semiotic function through a relational approach to modes and modalities (Oja, 2023).

The slogan "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu" functions as a multimodal semiotic complex where meaning arises through transduction across sensory modalities and semiotic modes, rather than from the text alone. Visually–textually, the slogan acts as a trigger that activates culturally sedimented auditory patterns – specifically rhythm, volume, and collective cadence – as it circulates in various cultural contexts like commemorations, cinema, and protests. This causes a shift from a visual-verbal mode to vocalized embodiment, where one hears or even mentally repeats the slogan's cadence. This auditory response then leads to a further shift into gestural and sensorimotor dimensions: the chant is paired with embodied gestures – most notably the raised fist – performed through embodied memory rather than conscious reflection; subconsciously, one feels like raising a fist. This gestural response is not fixed, as the slogan can be easily conflated with the similar one "Za domovino, s Titom naprej," causing embodied responses to vary between defiant fist-raising and salute-like postures shaped by pedagogical and ceremonial repetition.

These modal transitions are rooted in layered mnemonic structures – both personal and collective – condensed in iconic visual artifacts, most notably the photograph of Stjepan Filipović at the gallows (and its reproductions in statues and stamps), which functions as a visual condensation of resistance, sacrifice, and corporeal defiance. The slogan's semiotic force thus resides in a cascading affective economy where textual visibility, auditory resonance, visualization, and gestural embodiment strengthen one another within a localized

discursive universe (Eco et al., 1989), making its meaning inseparable from culturally specific multimodal memory and embodied practices through which it is repeatedly brought to life.

This account should be seen as an analytical reconstruction: it outlines a possible multimodal trajectory by extrapolating from the mnemonic abilities of the analyst and a nearby interpretive community. As a result, it runs the risk of mistaking such abilities for a generally available mnemonic mechanism. Empirically, the embodied layer of the slogan is unevenly distributed: for some, it is grounded in practiced vocalizations and ritualized bodily postures, while for others, it is mediated – learned through popular culture, commemorative media, or modern platforms – or both; the iconic photograph might be central, peripheral, or completely absent. What keeps the slogan's circulation going is not a stable, shared archive but a certain fuzziness – partial overlap between episodic and symbolic memory, personal recollections and collective repertoires, direct and culturally mediated embodiment. This very indeterminacy enables memetic adoption: the form stays recognizable enough to coordinate emotion and orientation, yet flexible enough to be re-anchored in different mnemonic resources, allowing vocal and bodily responses (such as standing, shouting, fist-raising, or salute-like postures) to remain variable enactments rather than uniform effects. The slogan functions as a complex mnemonic form – meme in the Dawkins's (1976) sense – before modern digital adaptations, as it condenses verbal, auditory, gestural, and emotional traces into a relatively stable yet internally diverse unit of political memory. When it circulates on social media platforms like X and Facebook, its mnemonic and political power is heightened through integration into composite artifacts – photos, caricatures, typographic variations, added framing, acronym reduction, and interactional layers like replies, comment threads, and visibility metrics. These transformations do not diminish its multimodal–embodied complexity; rather, they expand it into new environments, enabling the slogan to act both as a condensed mnemonic cue and as a dynamically recontextualized node within networked political memory practices.

This ability for resignification sets "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu" apart from other ritualized socialist slogans like "Za domovino, s Titom naprej," which, despite similar levels of institutional repetition and physical enactment, failed to re-emerge in later political struggles with the same force. The difference isn't in the level of ritualization itself, but in the slogan's capacity to define a normative boundary that stays relevant beyond its original historical context. While slogans focused on unity, development, or leadership were closely tied to the legitimacy of a specific political order, "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu" maintains a semiotically conflictual structure that can be reactivated whenever questions of authority, exclusion, and freedom come to the forefront. Its semiotic openness, paired with ritualized embodiment, makes it adaptable to a variety of discursive reconfigurations. The variety of posts on X and Facebook from the Slovenian context that utilize this slogan across commemorative, political, and everyday settings show not only its antagonistic power but also its ongoing agonistic potential. Rather than merely marking exclusion or opposition, the slogan functions as a reusable mnemonic resource that enables political disagreement, historical positioning, and normative claims to be expressed within a shared symbolic framework. Its continued circulation demonstrates a form of semiotic applicability that supports ongoing processes of agonistic memory formation, in which conflict is preserved as productive and open rather than being resolved or closed.

PLATFORM AFFORDANCES AS CONDITIONS OF MNEMONIC ACTION AND VISIBILITY

In this chapter, affordances are understood in Gibson's (2015) original sense: as action possibilities that emerge from the relationship between an organism and its environment. When applied to social media, this does not mean viewing platform features as deterministic causes or simplifying affordances to user perceptions. Instead, platforms serve as extended environments – material and symbolic infrastructures of perception and action – where historically ingrained mnemonic dispositions can be reactivated and reshaped. The central question is which platform affordances sustain the repeated reactivation of mnemonic forms within multimodal public exchanges.

Affordances have become a key analytical lens in social media platform studies for explaining how platform architectures enable and constrain communicative action, its visibility, and its interactive potential (Hutchby, 2001; boyd, 2011; Treem & Leonardi, 2012; Bucher & Helmond, 2018; Evans et al., 2017). What remains underexplored is how these actions become mnemonic and politically consequential by taking shape within specific multimodal and sensorial configurations of expression and embodiment.

Within communication and media scholarship focused on social media and digital memory, affective, discursive, and political dimensions have been more prominently theorized than multimodal and sensorial ones (e.g., Papacharissi, 2015; Ben-David et al., 2024). When multimodality is addressed, it is most often simplified to a general acknowledgment of the "multimedia" nature of platforms, mainly referring to the coexistence of text, images, audio, and video. What remains under-theorized is the relationship between modes and sensory modalities: how meaning is produced across them, how it is anchored in bodily perception, and how it acquires affective and ritual force. Approaches that combine affordance-based analysis with theories of multimodality are therefore uncommon, and even fewer studies explicitly integrate both traditions in a theoretically and methodologically explicit manner within research on digital and social media (notable exceptions include Reichl et al., 2022; van Leeuwen and Johannessen, 2022; Plastina, 2022). Nonetheless, such integrative frameworks are rarely used in research on digital memory. Consequently, affordance-based analyses often focus on what platforms enable users to do without explaining how (mnemonic) meaning is concretely and sensorially constructed through multimodal configurations.

This limitation matters for memory studies because remembering is an embodied and affective practice shaped by repetition, ritual, and sensory involvement. Visual forms, vocal intensity, rhythm, gestures, spatial arrangements, and collective synchronization all enhance mnemonic force. Without paying attention to these dimensions, affordances risk being seen as just technical or interactional potentials, detached from the environmental conditions that make mnemonic forms politically charged and socially mobilizing.

Social-semiotic multimodal theory has long explored how meaning is created across different modes and sensory channels, including how the affordances of semiotic resources both limit and support semiotic processes (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2001; Kress, 2010; Bateman et al., 2017). However, this perspective is rarely incorporated into affordance-based approaches to social media and digital memory, resulting in discussions about "what platforms allow" often lacking an explanation of how mnemonic force is produced and engaged through multimodal articulation. As previously mentioned, a helpful connection is offered by Campbell et al. (2019), who relate semiotic resources to Gibson's organism–environment relationship with sense-perceptive and motoric capabilities.

For the purposes of this article, Gibsonian affordances are therefore defined in relation to multimodal mnemonic circulation: the action possibilities through which historically sedimented mnemonic forms can be repeatedly brought into platformed public and contested. Affordances matter politically because they create potentials under which mnemonic interventions gain public traction and enter agonistic contestation.

In the case of “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu,” the relevant affordances are those that support (a) the inscription and re-inscription of the slogan (including abbreviation, quotation, and reformulation), (b) transduction across modes (embedding the slogan in images, videos, and typographic compositions, including remediations of iconic artifacts such as the Filipović photograph), (c) interactional uptake (reply threads and quote-post framing through which the slogan is reaffirmed, contested, or recontextualized), and (d) visibility modulation (feed ordering, algorithmic ranking, and engagement metrics that condition its platformed recirculation). Together, these affordances enable the slogan to operate as a repeatable and contestable mnemonic form rather than a static symbolic reference.

These affordances do not replace the slogan’s historically sedimented multimodal force; they modulate its circulation and activation. What changes under platform conditions is the speed and scope at which the slogan can be re-inscribed, recontextualized, and brought into interaction, intensifying cycles of reiteration and contestation central to its contemporary political efficacy. This efficacy is further sustained by the perceived public nature of platform environments: from users’ perspectives, mnemonic interventions appear to unfold within a seemingly open public sphere, even though the communication infrastructures are privately owned and controlled by algorithms. The feeling of participating in a shared, accessible space for political expression strengthens the slogan’s ability to serve as a public act of alignment, dissent, or provocation. However, the availability of these affordances does not guarantee equal political influence. Mnemonic engagement remains contingent on continued exposure and affective resonance – potentials that platform architectures and algorithmic filtering differentially enable and amplify.

The digital circulation of “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” shows how platform affordances reconfigure political memory. The slogan’s mnemonic force is not lessened in digital environments, but it becomes publicly operative through the platform-mediated dynamics that enable posts to circulate and provoke engagement. The following analysis explores how these features influence the slogan’s multimodal appearances and its contestation in today’s digital publics.

“SMRT FAŠIZMU, SVOBODA NARODU” ON X AND FACEBOOK

An analysis of contemporary uses of the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” on X and Facebook shows that it circulates less as a purely verbal statement and more as a multimodal mnemonic configuration in which text, images, and bodily gestures are tightly and affectively interwoven. Across posts, it functions as a conflicting sign whose political meaning is repeatedly reactivated and renegotiated in the present.

The analyzed posts do not form a single, uniform reference point but instead group into different ways of remembering. Across the material, six main patterns of reinterpretation can be observed. First (1), institutionalized commemorative uses, where the slogan appears in connection with officially recognized historical events and state holidays, such as the Slovenian

Day of Uprising Against the Occupier (27 April), functioning as a ritualized motto of institutionalized antifascist memory. Second (2), vernacular commemorative reaffirmations, in which users repeat the slogan alongside archival photographs, monuments, or references to partisan history, reaffirming the established antifascist narrative in a more informal digital context. Third (3), contemporary political adaptations, where the slogan is redeployed in current political conflicts by substituting new actors into its antagonistic structure. Fourth (4), counter-memory reinterpretations, which detach the slogan from its exclusive association with the Communist-led partisan movement and reconnect it to alternative antifascist traditions. Fifth (5), post-socialist delegitimizing reinterpretations, which recast the slogan as a symbol of communist domination or totalitarian rule. Finally (6), reflexive or critical inversions, in which the slogan is deliberately altered to expose the instability and manipulability of politically charged mnemonic expressions. These variations do not stand alone but frequently intersect and overlap, showing the slogan as a compact mnemonic symbol through which competing interpretations of the past and present are articulated.

The circulation of the slogan on social media is not always confined to clearly demarcated national or linguistic contexts. In some instances, posts referencing “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” intersect with wider post-Yugoslav mnemonic repertoires, including the Cyrillic script, Serbian or Croatian language versions, or symbols associated with a shared socialist past. While such overlaps complicate attempts to attribute mnemonic practices to a single national memory culture, they underscore the transnational mobility of antifascist symbols that cross borders and the open, fluid nature of platform-mediated memory. Content circulates across linguistic, cultural, and political boundaries and becomes available to conflicting appropriations.

Across the examined posts, a dominant visual genealogy of the slogan emerges. Archival photographs of WWII partisans, post-war propaganda posters, the red star, contemporary urban graffiti, and photographs of standing or saluting figures positioned next to inscriptions or memorials – especially during commemorative events associated with WWII battles, meetings, or anniversaries – recur with striking regularity. These images do not merely illustrate the slogan but anchor it in a continuity of embodied and spatial practices that connect different historical moments through the repetition of bodily postures, spatial arrangements, and modes of public appearance. In this way, the mnemonic force of the slogan is sustained both symbolically and through recognizable bodily dispositions that persist across media, contexts, and generations.

Alongside conflicting and polemical appropriations, a significant number of posts reinforce the slogan in an affirmative and commemorative register (figs. 7 and 9). These posts reproduce archival photographs of partisans, wartime documents, or iconic figures such as Stjepan Filipović, often accompanied by quotations, dates, and references to specific battles or anniversaries. In these cases, the slogan is not reinterpreted but reaffirmed as an ethical and historical axiom. Its meaning remains anchored in the antifascist struggle of WWII and is used as a sign of respect, continuity, or nostalgia. Here, the slogan acts as a stabilizing mnemonic device rather than a site of disruption. It reinforces an established narrative of antifascist legitimacy and effectively passes it down through generations, maintaining emotional ties to a heroic past. However, in such cases, the slogan usually implies a normative endorsement of the partisan and socialist historical narrative, framing it as the legitimate or morally authoritative trajectory of anti-fascist struggle. As a result, these invocations often generate counter-posts and revisionist responses that contest this implicit claim to historical legitimacy.

Figure 7: Facebook post commemorating the destruction of the Partisan hospital Franja, accompanied by archival photographs of Partisan fighters and the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu.” Such posts reproduce and reinforce the dominant antifascist narrative in which the Partisan movement is framed as the force that liberated the territory from Axis occupation, reaffirming the slogan within a commemorative and legitimizing register.

The slogan is often paired with visual symbols linked to socialist and antifascist iconography, most notably the red star (fig. 8). In this context, the red star does not function merely as a referential sign of communism but as a condensed visual mnemonic device. It encapsulates ideological positioning, affective alignment, and claims of historical continuity into an immediately recognizable form. Through its recurrent presence, the slogan is anchored within a shared visual repertoire that exceeds propositional meaning and operates at the level of embodied recognition. At the same time, the red star’s circulation across contemporary anti-imperialist, antifascist, anti-populist, and anti-nationalist contexts reveals the fragmented and contested nature of collective memory, as the same symbol can be adopted for different political appropriations.

Figure 8: Post on X pairing the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” with the red star and the hammer and sickle—symbols closely associated with socialist and antifascist iconography. In this configuration, the red star operates as a condensed visual mnemonic device that anchors the slogan within a recognizable socialist visual repertoire and signals ideological alignment with antifascist and leftist historical narratives.

The slogan in its original form is frequently shared on social media in connection with the Slovenian national holiday Day of Uprising Against the Occupier (27 April), which was known as the Day of the Liberation Front from 1948 to 1992. The Liberation Front was a political organization established in Ljubljana on 26 April 1941 as the Anti-Imperialist Front. After Germany attacked the Soviet Union, it was renamed the Liberation Front of the Slovene Nation. In this context, the slogan functions as a guiding motto of the commemorative holiday (figs. 9 and 10).

Figures 9 and 10: Posts on social media marking Slovenia’s national holiday Day of Uprising Against the Occupier (27 April). Left (9): an X post reproducing the iconic photograph of the partisan Stjepan Filipović with the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu,” shared in connection with the commemorative date. Right (10): a Facebook post in which a musician dedicates a song to the holiday, followed by further posts that repeat the slogan and explicitly link it to the historical legacy of the Liberation Front (Osvobodilna fronta). In such cases, the slogan functions as a guiding motto of the commemorative event, reaffirming the established antifascist narrative associated with the Liberation Front.

During the anti-government protests that took place in Slovenia between 2020 and 2022, in the context of the COVID-19 containment measures, protesters coined the slogan “Smrt janšizmu, svoboda narodu” (“Death to Janšism, freedom to the people”), which appeared on banners, placards, and other protest materials. At the time, the Slovenian government was led by the right-leaning politician Janez Janša. Many protesters perceived the government’s

measures as authoritarian and mobilized against the government, calling for political change. After the parliamentary elections of April 2022, which brought the left-leaning politician Robert Golob to power, the slogan did not disappear from public discourse but continued to circulate on social media. Especially after 2023, it appears frequently in the form “Smrt janšizmu, svoboda narodu” or in the expanded formulation “Smrt fašizmu, smrt janšizmu, svoboda narodu.” In some cases, the phrase is invoked around the anniversary of the 2022 parliamentary elections (figs. 11 and 12), where it functions as an informal commemorative marker of the political transition.

Figures 11 and 12: Posts on X illustrating the contemporary adaptation of the slogan in connection with Slovenian electoral politics. The expanded formulation “Smrt fašizmu, smrt janšizmu, 22svoboda narodu,” and the shortened version “Smrt janšizmu, 22svoboda narodu,” appear alongside symbols associated with the Liberation Front (OF) and the red star. Circulating around the anniversary of the 2022 parliamentary elections that brought a change of government, these posts reinterpret the historical slogan within a present-day political context, framing it as a celebratory marker of political transition and as a continuation of antifascist symbolic language in contemporary partisan discourse.

In September 2020, the Slovenian prosecution dismissed a request to prohibit the public display of banners carrying this slogan, a decision that supporters of the protests widely celebrated and commented on social media (fig. 13). The continued circulation of the slogan has also generated political controversy. In 2025, the parliamentary group of the Slovenian Democratic Party (SDS), led by Janez Janša, addressed a question to the government asking whether the dissemination of the slogan could be sanctioned under proposed legislation addressing hate speech, arguing that it incites hostility toward political opponents (figs. 14 and 15).

← Post

neencuzurianski
@neencuzurianski

Tožilstvo odločilo razjvanje in nošenje transparentov s parolo "SMRT JANSIZMLU, SVOBODA NARODU" ni kaznivno dejanje grožnje. Kazenska ovedba @jansizmlu je zavržena.

12:53 PM · Sep 3, 2020

30

50

110

1

Relevant

View quotes

Post your reply

Reply

Tjasa Zavrh @TjasaZavrh · Sep 3, 2020
Sveč (in bo zmeda) k hrvosodjem

Lukajlg @lukajlg827 · Sep 3, 2020
Sveč, ajno vas SMRT JANSIZMLU, SVOBODA NARODU. Lahko nam pušča k...!!!!

Frekk Mate @FrekkMate · Sep 3, 2020
Pot v državljansko vojno je s tem odjeto.

Franc Zoro @FrancZoro · Sep 3, 2020
Globoka država s pomočniki za ohranitev statusa ričice borbu za in s negiranjem zgodovine, dela na polito. Da ne omenjam strano zvest tistim, kar bo padlo iz omaz. Ji boste zmagali na naslednjih volitvah pokobil v narode. Sprejedeni ste. Le tako rapelj in hvata s imenu normalnosti.

Honda & Robert @HondaTheBest11 · Sep 3, 2020
Ting bo potvrdeno pamerjeji le tožilstvo

ChesGuvera @Ches27Che · Sep 3, 2020

Karath Stizale @StizaleKX · Sep 3, 2020
a bo sef Vrhovnega Drzavnega tozilstva naslednji na nočni korespondenci naj vlade?

AlexKocman @AlexKocman · Sep 3, 2020
Pravilno Common sense!

Alex K. @AlexKov1 · Sep 3, 2020

ChesGuvera @Ches27Che · Sep 3, 2020

Karath Stizale @StizaleKX · Sep 3, 2020
a bo sef Vrhovnega Drzavnega tozilstva naslednji na nočni korespondenci naj vlade?

AlexKocman @AlexKocman · Sep 3, 2020
Pravilno Common sense!

Alex K. @AlexKov1 · Sep 3, 2020
Piska - pa je res v Sloveniji problem z vladašvno pravo.

Silvester Minar @vesterm1 · Sep 3, 2020
Potemstajem, tudi "smrt tožilstvo svoboda narodu" ni kaznivno dejanje.

John Locke @JohnLock4872445 · Sep 3, 2020
Sveč tožilstvo!

Repi sende @repi1981 · Sep 3, 2020
Kaj si, vladašvna prava?

Dane @Dane384215 · Sep 3, 2020
Bravo

milan bertom @milan121 · Sep 4, 2020
A se veselite

Stanislav Račel @ra19803 · Sep 4, 2020
Tožilstvo, zdaj pa prište v EU, kako vas Ji maštrina.

Danica @Danica73833585 · Sep 3, 2020
Saj ne more bit drugak? Zda pa napad Ji na tožilstvo!

Silvester Minar @vesterm1 · Sep 3, 2020
Smo vedeli da je to tožilstvo Kučanovi, sedaj so to samo znova potrdili.

Silvester Minar @vesterm1 · Sep 3, 2020
Kako bo tožilstvo pregrajalo zlo, če je samo zlo?

Stanislav Račel @ra19803 · Sep 4, 2020
Tožilstvo, zdaj pa prište v EU, kako vas Ji maštrina.

Danica @Danica73833585 · Sep 3, 2020
Saj ne more bit drugak? Zda pa napad Ji na tožilstvo!

Silvester Minar @vesterm1 · Sep 3, 2020
Smo vedeli da je to tožilstvo Kučanovi, sedaj so to samo znova potrdili.

Silvester Minar @vesterm1 · Sep 3, 2020
Kako bo tožilstvo pregrajalo zlo, če je samo zlo?

Silvester Minar @vesterm1 · Sep 3, 2020
Tožilstvo ponovno dokazalo, da je komunistično in zločinsko.

DaneS6 @Dane45810 · Sep 3, 2020
Kdo si pa upa sina "0 obtožb? Ro očka takoj urgiral po zgledu vrhovnega sodišča. Obe in sim "0, dve 0

veronika @veronika80203543 · Sep 4, 2020
Pa to ne moreš verjet, nedopustno!

Danica @Danica73833585 · Sep 3, 2020
No no potem pa bi moralo po vseki ki trdit da tožilstvo ne dela prav obtožbe tudi vse vas, ki ljudi zmejejo s komunistični kajnot?

Probable spam

Tomaz Kogovnik @TKogovnik · Sep 4, 2020
SMRT FAJONSZMLU!

Figure 13: Thread of responses on X reacting to a post by the media outlet *Necenzurirano* reporting that the Slovenian prosecution had dismissed a request to prohibit the display of banners bearing the slogan “Smrt janšizmu, 24svoboda narodu” (September 2020). The decision was widely circulated and celebrated by users supportive of the anti-government protests, generating numerous comments that repeat or endorse the slogan. The example illustrates how legal and media events can trigger intensified circulation of the slogan on social media, where users collectively reaffirm and amplify it within a politically polarized discussion.

Figures 14 and 15: Posts on X illustrating critical reactions to the slogan “Smrt janšizmu, 24svobod24a narodu.” Left: a post by the parliamentary group of the Slovenian Democratic Party (SDS) questioning whether the dissemination of the slogan should be sanctioned under proposed legislation addressing hate speech. Right: a post by another account amplifying the same message through a video excerpt from a parliamentary debate. These posts frame the slogan as an incitement to hostility against political opponents, demonstrating how its circulation generates counter-discourses that challenge its legitimacy in the contemporary political arena.

In recent years, the adapted slogan has continued to circulate even after the political context that originally produced it had changed. Variants such as “Smrt janšizmu, svoboda narodu” and the expanded form “Smrt fašizmu, smrt janšizmu, svoboda narodu” appear particularly frequently after 2023, when the government had already been taken over by Robert Golob, whose electoral victory in 2022 had been supported by the earlier protesters. In this new context, the slogan no longer functions primarily as a direct oppositional cry against an incumbent government, as it did during the anti-government protests of 2020–2022. Instead, its function shifts toward a more complex mnemonic and political register. The slogan's reformulations simultaneously evoke several historical layers: the original wartime antifascist resistance, the socialist period in which that resistance was institutionally commemorated and ritualized, and the anti-government protest mobilizations of 2020–2022 directed against Janez Janša's third administration. Through this layered mnemonic reference, the slogan increasingly operates as a symbolic reminder of earlier political struggles. At the same time, its continued repetition in digital environments maintains a clear motivational dimension. As Slovenia approaches the parliamentary elections scheduled for March 2026, the slogan is frequently used as a form of political mobilization that draws on antifascist memory to reinforce support within a particular political camp.

A rarer but illustrative variation appears in the slogan “Smrt golobizmu, svoboda narodu,” which emerged shortly after the change of government in 2022 (fig. 16). This formulation can be understood as a reactive inversion of the much more widespread slogan “Smrt janšizmu, svoboda narodu.” By inserting a different political figure into the same antagonistic structure,

the slogan demonstrates how its formulation can be redeployed by opposing actors as a vehicle of political criticism directed at the government of Robert Golob. Although such examples are far less common, they reveal the structural openness of the phrase: its oppositional semiotic structure allows different political adversaries to occupy the same position within the formulaic configuration..

Figure 16: Facebook post featuring the slogan “Smrt golobizmu, svoboda narodu” (“Death to Golobism, freedom to the people”), published shortly after the change of government in 2022. By substituting “Golobism” for the original target of the adapted slogan “Smrt janšizmu, svoboda narodu,” the post illustrates a reactive inversion of the slogan, demonstrating how the same antagonistic semiotic structure can be redeployed by opposing actors as a vehicle of political criticism directed at the government of Robert Golob.

In some cases, the slogan is also linked to a broader geopolitical framework. For instance, the phrase “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” appears alongside expressions such as “Long live Vladimir Putin” and “Long live Russia,” framing contemporary geopolitical conflict through the symbolic language of antifascist struggle (fig. 17). Such uses extend the slogan’s mnemonic field beyond the national historical context and implicitly revive the earlier symbolic alignment between Yugoslav communist resistance, the Soviet Union and anti-imperialism. In this sense, the slogan demonstrates a form of mnemonic mobility, whereby antifascist memory is reactivated within new geopolitical narratives.

Figure 17: Facebook post presenting Vladimir Putin as a global liberator and the only effective counterforce to Western power, invoking the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” to frame contemporary conflict through a revived anti-imperialist imaginary.

In some cases, the slogan is being reframed in ways that activate counter-memory. For example, political activist Vili Kovačič presents it as a “TIGR greeting,” referencing the anti-

fascist organization TIGR that operated in the Slovene Littoral before and during WWII (fig. 18). Through this reframing, the slogan is detached from its exclusive association with the Communist-led partisan movement and reconnected to a broader, non-communist lineage of anti-fascist resistance. This reinterpretation brings to the surface memories that had been marginalized within the socialist symbolic order, where the antifascist struggle was narratively unified under the Partisan movement and the Communist Party. By invoking TIGR, the slogan becomes a site where suppressed or subordinated strands of resistance history resurface, recalling actors who fought against fascist occupation and advocated for the freedom of the local population but were later overshadowed or ideologically neutralized in the dominant post-war narrative. In this way, the slogan functions as a vehicle of counter-memory: it destabilizes the previously hegemonic memory regime and reopens the questions about who constitutes the legitimate subject of antifascist struggle. Instead of merely repeating an established historical script, it becomes a discursive space where competing memories of resistance are articulated and renegotiated.

Figure 18: Post on X by political activist Vili Kovačič reframing the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” as a “TIGR greeting.” By linking the slogan to the anti-fascist organization TIGR, which operated in the Slovene Littoral before and during WWII, the post reinterprets the slogan outside its exclusive association with the Communist-led partisan movement and reconnects it to a broader, non-communist tradition of anti-fascist resistance, thereby activating a counter-memory of the antifascist struggle.

In post-socialist critique, the slogan undergoes a radical reinterpretation. One X post claims that “Death to Fascism, Freedom to the People” actually meant “Death to the fascist, power to the communist” (fig. 19). Here, the slogan is separated from its antifascist origins and reinterpreted as a concise expression of communist dominance. What was once a call for collective liberation is reclassified as a tool for ideological consolidation. This interpretation presents a critical political judgment. The slogan is seen as evidence of ongoing totalitarianism and is often dismissed as an illegitimate remnant of an authoritarian past. Through this reinterpretation, antifascism itself is destabilized as a moral and political benchmark, and the slogan becomes a proxy for broader disputes over the legitimacy of the socialist era. In this way, the slogan becomes a battleground where the meaning of the past is actively contested today. Its semantic structure is reopened and reinterpreted, not to expand its emancipatory potential, but to invert its moral significance. The fight over the slogan thus reflects a broader

struggle over historical authority, political legitimacy, and the narrative framing of the twentieth century.

Figure 19: Post on X by Matej Rigelnik presenting a post-socialist critique of the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu.” The post argues that the phrase in practice meant “death to the fascist, power to the communist,” thereby reinterpreting the slogan not as a call for liberation but as an expression of communist domination. Through this reframing, the slogan is detached from its antifascist origins and recast as a symbol of ideological control associated with the socialist regime.

In another example from X (fig. 20), the slogan undergoes a mnemonic reversal, redirecting antifascist rhetoric against the current government. The phrase “Death to Fascism, Freedom to the People” is used in a post targeting Prime Minister Robert Golob, a left-leaning politician who currently holds executive power. While Golob has previously called out the former government as fascist, this post reverses the accusation, blaming him for fascism. The reinterpretation occurs on multiple levels. The statement, typographically added on the collage – “My grandfather was a fascist,” adds a genealogical layer, personalizing the accusation and symbolically linking the Prime Minister to a stigmatized historical lineage. This shifts the debate from policy criticism to a moral and historical attack. The visual pairing of Golob with Hitler and Mussolini further erases the time gap, equating today’s democratic leadership with key figures of 20th-century fascism. In this context, the slogan acts as a call for political change. Calling the Prime Minister fascist suggests that his removal from office would lead to freedom for the people. This results in a mnemonic reversal: the language of antifascist resistance is turned against a government that claims the antifascist tradition, disrupting traditional memory alignments and reinterpreting the meaning of fascism in today’s political landscape.

Figure 20: Post on X combining the slogan “Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu” with a visual collage juxtaposing Prime Minister Robert Golob with historical fascist leaders. By inserting a contemporary political figure into the antifascist visual and rhetorical framework, the post illustrates a mnemonic reversal in which antifascist symbolism is redeployed to target a government that claims the antifascist tradition.

Another form of reinterpretation appears in the field of contemporary art. The artist Maja Bajević engages with the slogan by inverting its structure in the neon installation *Freedom to Fascism, Death to the People* (2025) (fig. 21). By reversing the original formulation, the work produces an intentionally absurd statement that exposes how easily the meaning of historically charged slogans can be distorted. The intervention can be read as a critical response to revisionist reinterpretations of socialist and antifascist history, particularly to contemporary narratives that question or relativize the achievements of the partisan movement and the antifascist struggle. The installation was presented in an exhibition running from 27 June 2025 to 4 January 2026, situating the work within a politically sensitive moment preceding the parliamentary elections in Slovenia. In this context, the inversion of the slogan can also be understood as a politicization of art: by drawing attention to the instability of mnemonic formulas and their ideological manipulation, the artwork intervenes in ongoing public debates about historical memory, political legitimacy, and the interpretation of the socialist past.

Figure 21: Facebook post published on 16 December 2025 presenting Maja Bajević's neon installation Freedom to Fascism, Death to the People (2025), accompanied by the official explanation of the Museum of Contemporary Art Metelkova (MSUM), which interprets the work as a critique of historical revisionism. Appearing in a period when public discourse in Slovenia was already strongly marked by the approaching parliamentary elections, the artistic intervention can also be read within the broader politicized context of contemporary debates over antifascist memory and the socialist legacy.

Taken together, these modes of circulation indicate that the slogan functions less as a stable form of remembrance and more as a recurring source of disruption within the contemporary memory landscape. It challenges both the socialist narrative of antifascist continuity and the post-socialist narrative of democratic rupture, reopening conflicts that dominant memory regimes try to close. Instead of serving as a neatly finished historical reference, it consistently reactivates debates over political legitimacy and historical responsibility, thereby eliciting strong affective responses and renewed polarization.

The repeated circulation of the photograph of Stjepan Filipović shows how this mnemonic persistence is maintained. The image often appears alongside the slogan or circulates on its own as a compact visual icon. For those that grew up in socialist Yugoslavia, its associated bodily dispositions may be linked to episodic memory of institutional rituals and public commemorations; for later generations, these dispositions are acquired through mediated repetition and even reenactment – posing with raised fists, staging the gesture for the camera, and sharing it online. In this way, digital artifacts do not just represent the slogan but also participate in the reactivation of its embodied repertoire. This dynamic can be understood as semio-somatic memory: a mode of remembering where semiotic signs and bodily dispositions are intertwined. Memory here is not confined to narrative recall but is enacted through posture, gesture, vocalization, and affective alignment. The slogan's contemporary efficacy rests on this embodied sedimentation. Even when detailed historical knowledge is partial or absent, the repetition of recognizable gestures and signs sustains mnemonic continuity across generations and political orders.

The endurance of the slogan shows how historically embodied mnemonic forms can traverse regimes and reappear in public space as arenas of ongoing struggle. Having lost its previous roles as a tool for resistance uprising and later for state legitimation, it persists as a politically charged mnemonic form whose force derives from multimodal recognition and embodied repetition.

CONCLUSION: PLATFORMED MEMORY AND AGONISTIC PUBLIC CONTESTATION

Representational accounts and generalized affordance models are inadequate to explain the political significance of digital memory. The analysis shows that memory becomes politically active in platformed environments by activating historically sedimented mnemonic forms under socio-technical conditions that shape their capacity to appear, circulate and be contested about. The issue is not about replacing institutional memory regimes with vernacular ones but about reconfiguring how mnemonic power is created and contested in public.

Central to this reconfiguration is the interaction between *semio-somatic* organization and platform affordances. The slogan's oppositional semiotic structure and its embodied sedimentation provide the conditions for mnemonic endurance; platform affordances, understood in a Gibsonian sense as relational potentials for action within extended environments of perception and communication, modulate how it reappears and enters public dispute. Affordances do not determine meaning but condition the repeated inscription, multimodal rearticulation, and interactional engagement through which historically charged forms enter agonistic public contestation. Memory on platforms thus functions as a field of mediated activation, where embodied mnemonic structures are continually exposed to reaffirmation, reinterpretation, and antagonistic appropriation.

The case of "Smrt fašizmu, svoboda narodu" demonstrates that mnemonic endurance relies not only on ritualization and embodiment but also on semiotic structure. The slogan's oppositional setup – combining negation with emancipation – directly encodes political antagonism into its linguistic form. This relational structure allows different actors, opponents, and groups to be incorporated into its unchanging syntagmatic framework, maintaining continuity of form while allowing paradigmatic variability. Its ability to be reinterpreted, and thus remain politically relevant over time, comes from this structural flexibility combined with embodied sedimentation.

The slogan's current circulation shows how digital platforms serve as spaces for competitive public memory. Its various appearances – ranging from institutionalized commemorative uses and vernacular commemorative reaffirmations to contemporary political adaptations, counter-memory reinterpretations, post-socialist delegitimizing reinterpretations, and reflexive or critical inversions – demonstrate that its survival doesn't depend on stable meaning but on ongoing contestation. These different yet related modes of expression confirm that mnemonic power in digital spaces works through repetition and conflict rather than agreement. Repeated disputes over the slogan do not indicate mnemonic decline but highlight the ongoing political importance of embodied antifascist memory as a contemporary resource in struggles over who may legitimately speak for the political community and on what normative grounds.

To understand this condition, the article has proposed the notion of *memorification*: the rapid activation and recycling of historically sedimented mnemonic forms within algorithmically structured environments. Memorification does not undo memory's embodied foundation; it amplifies its exposure to repetition and conflict. The political efficacy of digital memory, therefore, depends on the interaction of semiotic structure, embodied sedimentation, and platform-driven visibility.

Future research should further develop a relational multimodal approach capable of analyzing how semiotic modes, sensory modalities, embodied practices, and affordances co-constitute mnemonic force in digital publics. Only through such integration can the dynamics of memorification be properly understood as a key feature of contemporary political memory.

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